

26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators
"From Global Indicators to Local Applications"

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STI 2022 Conference Proceedings

Proceedings of the 26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators

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Citation: Hare, M., & Mongeon, P.(2022). The Impact of Mentorship on the Research Performance of LIS PhDs. In N. Robinson-Garcia, D. Torres-Salinas, & W. Arroyo-Machado (Eds.), *26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators*, STI 2022 (sti22215). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6956737>

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26th International Conference on Science and Technology Indicators | STI 2022

“From Global Indicators to Local Applications”

7-9 September 2022 | Granada, Spain

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The Impact of Mentorship on the Research Performance of LIS PhDs

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Introduction

Doctoral mentorship has been described as the most significant relationship in a student's academic career (Ma et al., 2020) and can affect the mentee in psychosocial and instrumental capacities (Kram, 1985). While several studies looking at the relationship between mentorship and research productivity (Malmgren et al., 2010; Paglis et al., 2006; Sugimoto et al., 2011) point to some increase in productivity due to mentorship (Marsh, 2017, pg. 1131), much is still unknown about how mentorship affects the careers of protégés (Liénard et al., 2018).

Despite the importance of mentorship relationships, Ma et al. (2020) show that STEM students achieve their highest impact when they break from their advisor's research topics and display intellectual independence (Ma et. al, 2020).

This work-in-progress explores the relationship between publishing patterns of students and their advisors in LIS in North America to better understand the influence advisors have on the academic careers of their students.¹ Studying these outcomes will contribute to scholarship on the value of doctoral mentorship in LIS and its impact on student academic success. It will offer broader understandings about the interconnectedness of the academic LIS network in North America, authorship, and advisor-advisee scholarly interaction and output.

RQ1: How does the research productivity and impact of advisors relate to that of the productivity and impact of the advisees?

RQ2: How does the similarity between the advisee's doctoral thesis and the advisor's prior work relate to advisees' productivity and impact?

RQ3: How does advisor-advisee collaboration relate to the advisees' productivity and impact?

Methods

We retrieved all records from the ProQuest dissertation and thesis database from 2008-2012 using the search string: ““library science” or “library studies” or “information science” or “information studies” or “archival science” or “archival studies” or “ischool””. We then retrieved publications authored by matching the Ph.D. students and the advisor to

algorithmically disambiguated Web of Science (WoS) authors (Caron & van Eck, 2014). For this analysis, we focused on precision and used a strict set of criteria for the matching. First, we selected only authors matching on the full first and last name and affiliated to the institution granting the Ph.D. degree for the dissertation, and only considered WoS authors with at least 2 publications. To further eliminate false positives, we only considered cases where the year of the first publication of the student came later than that of the potential advisor, and for which both the student and the advisor had a single WoS author match. This resulted in a dataset of 312 advisee-advisor pairs.

In our analysis, we consider four variables: *productivity* defined as the average number of publications per year; *impact* operationalized by the average citation normalized by WoS subject categories and publication year (MNCS); the *similarity* between advisor and advisees' research interests measured by the maximum cosine similarity between the title and abstract of the dissertation and all the prior publications of the advisor that were not co-authored by the student; and *advisor-advisee collaboration*, which is a dichotomous variable indicating whether the advisor and advisee have co-authored at least one publication.

Results

In this section we first report on the relationship between each variable of interest and the productivity and impact of advisees, and then combine the variables in two multiple linear regression models. In Figure 1, both the productivity and the MNCS of advisors appear to have a positive influence on the advisees' productivity and MNCS. The slope of the linear regression is steeper for the MNCS.

Figure 1. Relationship between the advisors' and advisees' productivity (left) and impact (right)

As we can see in Figure 2, the influence of the PhD dissertation similarity to the advisor's prior research on advisees' productivity and impact is positive, although it is very weak for the

MNCS. The effect is weaker than the influence of productivity and impact observed in Figure 1.

Figure 2. Relationship between the similarity of the advisee's dissertation and the advisor's past research and advisee's productivity (left) and impact (right)

In Figure 3, we see that co-authoring at least one publication with the advisor increases the average productivity and MNCS of advisees. The effects appear to be of similar amplitude for both variables. Additionally, most PhD students tend to publish at least one paper with their advisors.

Figure 3. Relationship between advisor-advisee collaboration and advisees' productivity (left) and impact (right)

We report below the coefficients of two linear regression models that aim to predict advisee's productivity (Table 1) and impact (Table 2) based on the 4 variables explored in Figure 1, 2 and 3. Overall, the models have limited predictive value as they only explain 5% and 23% of the

variance in advisees' productivity and impact, respectively. While most effects appear to be insignificant, there appears to be a statistically significant association between the similarity of the PhD dissertation and the advisors' past work, as well as a nearly statistically significant (although very weak) association between the advisors' and advisees' productivity (Table 1). There also appears to be a positive and statistically significant association between the advisors' MNCS and the advisee's MNCS.

Table 1. Linear regression model predicting advisees' productivity

	Estimate	S.E.	t	P-value
Intercept	0.76	0.29	2.59	0.01
Collaboration	0.12	0.22	0.55	0.59
Advisor MNCS	0.01	0.03	0.30	0.76
Advisor productivity	0.00	0.00	1.80	0.07
Similarity	1.24	0.38	3.28	0.00

Table 2. Linear regression model predicting advisees' impact

	Estimate	S.E.	t	P-value
Intercept	0.67	0.39	1.70	0.09
Collaboration	0.33	0.29	1.12	0.26
Advisor MNCS	0.37	0.04	9.22	0.00
Advisor productivity	0.00	0.00	0.34	0.73
Similarity	0.12	0.51	0.23	0.82

Discussion and conclusion

The findings of our study suggest that the doctoral mentorship relationship may play a significant role in student research performance in terms of both output and impact. The models explain 5% of the variance in productivity and 23% of the variance in impact, which indicates that while choosing the right advisor may positively influence one's academic achievements, that decision alone does not tend to make or break one's research career. The doctoral experience cannot be reduced to the advisor-advisee relationship. Additional factors, such as evolving in an intellectually stimulating environment, affect performance – more in fact than the quality and frequency of one-to-one interactions with advisors (Yvalnez, 2017). These different degrees of mentorship relationships, such as coordination, cooperation, and collaboration (Gunawardena et al. 2010), are not captured in our data.

The results also suggest that providing co-authorship opportunities may be a good way for advisors to support their advisees, as it helps increase their research output and impact. Collaboration may be facilitated by students sharing research interests with their advisors, as suggested by the positive relationship between productivity and the similarity of the PhD dissertation and the advisor's past work. The benefits of working closely with one's advisor can conflict with the importance of establishing one's independence as a researcher. Giving students the liberty to diversify their research interests may ultimately provide greater career advantages as they evolve in their careers (Ma et al., 2020).

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ⁱ The terms mentor and mentee are used in reference to the holistic relationship of the mentor and student in conjunction with other non-instrumental benefits. We use the terms advisor and advisee to discuss the dyad working as a research unit.